

Hydrological and Water Quality Modeling Using SWAT in the Deji Reservoir Watershed, Taiwan

Supplemental Technical Report for the manuscript:

*Characterizing Watershed–Reservoir Interactions and Water Quality Dynamics
under Climate Change: A Coupled Modeling Approach*

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Executive Summary

This report presents the development, calibration, and application of a hydrological and water quality model for the Deji Reservoir catchment using the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT). The model was implemented in QSWAT3 (version 2.0.1) within QGIS 3.40.4 to simulate streamflow, sediment load, and total phosphorus (TP) dynamics over the period 2012–2021.

The watershed was discretized into 31 subbasins and 703 hydrologic response units (HRUs) to enable representation of spatial variability in land use, soil, and topography. Model calibration and validation were conducted using observed data from two gauging stations for the periods 2014–2018 and 2019–2021, respectively.

Model performance was satisfactory for streamflow and sediment load, with Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency values mostly above 0.5, indicating good agreement between simulated and observed data. The model effectively captured temporal variability and overall trends in hydrological and sediment processes. In contrast, TP simulations exhibited greater uncertainty and lower performance, which reflects the limitations in input data and the inherent complexity of nutrient processes, including fertilizer application and point source characterization. Sediment loads exhibited a stronger dependence on discharge, whereas TP dynamics showed greater variability due to more complex transport and biogeochemical processes.

The SWAT model effectively represents watershed-scale hydrological and sediment dynamics in the Deji Reservoir catchment. While results for TP should be interpreted with caution, the model is suitable for scenario-based analysis and can support water resource management applications, including the evaluation of sediment and nutrient control strategies under changing environmental conditions.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background

The Deji Reservoir catchment in central Taiwan is an important water resource system that supports hydropower generation, water supply, and ecosystem functions. The catchment is characterized by mountainous terrain, frequent rainfall events, and diverse land use, which contribute to substantial variability in hydrological processes, sediment transport, and nutrient loading. These processes have important implications for reservoir sedimentation and water quality, which are concerns for long-term reservoir operation and management.

Assessment of watershed processes in the Deji Reservoir catchment is supported by multiple monitoring stations that provide spatial and temporal observations. However, while these data offer point-based information, they cannot fully represent watershed-scale dynamics of streamflow, sediment yield, and nutrient transport. Therefore, modeling approaches are used to integrate available data and support scenario-based analysis under varying environmental and management conditions.

The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) is a semi-distributed, process-based model widely used to simulate hydrological processes and water quality at the watershed scale [1, 2]. Its ability to represent spatial variability in topography, land use, and soil properties makes it suitable for application in the Deji Reservoir watershed [3].

In this study, the SWAT model is applied to simulate hydrological and water quality processes in the Deji Reservoir catchment.

1.2 Objective

The objective of this study is to develop, calibrate, and apply the SWAT model to simulate hydrological and water quality processes in the Deji Reservoir catchment, including streamflow, sediment load, and total phosphorus load. This report presents the model development, calibration and validation, and results for the simulation period from 2012 to 2021.

1.3 Study area

The Deji Reservoir is located in the upper reaches of the Dajia River in central Taiwan (Figure 1) and was formed by a 180 m high and 290 m long concrete thin arch dam completed in 1974, with a total storage capacity of approximately 188 million m³ [4]. The reservoir has a maximum water surface elevation of 1,408 m above sea level (masl) and a bottom elevation of 1,318 masl. The contributing catchment area is approximately 600 km², with elevations ranging from 1,407 masl at the reservoir to 3,880 masl at the headwaters, which originate from Nanhu Mountain in the Central Mountain Range.

As shown in Figure 1, the watershed outlet is located at the downstream end of the reservoir and is labeled as outlet 4. Outlet 3 represents the inflow point to the reservoir, while outlets 1 and 2 correspond to the gauging stations used for streamflow and water quality monitoring (Hehuanshan and Chichiawan stations, respectively). In addition, three point source locations are included in the model, as indicated in the figure.

Figure 1. Location of the Deji Reservoir catchment.

2 Model development

The SWAT model was developed using spatial and meteorological datasets, including a digital elevation model (DEM), land use and land cover map, soil map, and meteorological data (i.e., precipitation, air temperature, relative humidity, solar radiation, and wind speed). These datasets were used to represent watershed characteristics and to provide climatic forcing for the simulations.

Watershed delineation and stream network generation were automatically performed using the DEM within the SWAT framework. Subsequently, HRUs were defined based on unique combinations of land use, soil type, and slope. No threshold values were applied during HRU definition; thus, all possible HRU classes were retained to preserve spatial detail.

2.1 Datasets used

A DEM was used as the primary input for watershed delineation and slope derivation in the SWAT model. The DEM was obtained from a Taiwan government dataset, with a spatial resolution of

20 m, and was projected to the TWD97 coordinate system (EPSG 3826). The dataset was pre-processed within the QGIS environment prior to model setup.

Land use and land cover (LULC) data for the Deji Reservoir catchment were obtained from the Ministry of the Interior. The watershed is dominated by forested areas, which together account for approximately 84.04% of the total watershed area. Mixed forest (FRST) represents the largest proportion at 64.11%, followed by deciduous forest (FRSD) at 19.66%, while evergreen forest (FRSE) contributes a minor fraction of 0.27%. Agricultural land (AGRL) covers 7.92% of the watershed. Wetland areas, including forested (WETF) and non-forested (WETN) wetlands, account for 1.88% and 4.11%, respectively, while open water (WATR) comprises 1.58% of the total area. Urban land uses, including low-density (URLD) and medium-density (URMD) development, together with transportation areas (UTRN), collectively account for less than 0.5% of the watershed. A summary of the LULC distribution is provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Land use land cover classes in Deji Reservoir catchment.

LULC Code	% Watershed	Description
AGRL	7.92	Agricultural Land (Generic Cropland)
FRSD	19.66	Forest–Deciduous
FRSE	0.27	Forest–Evergreen
FRST	64.11	Forest–Mixed
URLD	0.14	Urban Land–Low Density
URMD	0.20	Urban Land–Medium Density
UTRN	0.13	Transportation
WATR	1.58	Water
WETF	1.88	Wetlands–Forested
WETN	4.11	Wetlands–Non-Forested

Spatial soil data for the Deji Reservoir catchment were obtained from the Ministry of Agriculture. The dataset represents the entire watershed as a single undifferentiated soil type. Initial soil properties required for SWAT modeling, including hydraulic conductivity, bulk density, and available water capacity, were estimated based on soil information from the Taiwan Soil Survey Geographic Database (TSSURGO) prior to model calibration.

Slope classification in the Deji Reservoir catchment was derived from the DEM and categorized into five classes (0–15%, 15–30%, 30–45%, 45–55%, and > 55%) to represent variations in terrain steepness and their influence on hydrological and erosion processes. As shown in Table 2, the watershed is characterized by predominantly steep slopes, with areas exceeding 55% slope accounting for approximately 69.81% of the total area. This distribution reflects the highly mountainous nature of the catchment and has significant implications for runoff generation, sediment transport, and overall watershed response.

Table 2. Slope classes and their corresponding percentage of the watershed area.

Slope	% Watershed
0–15	9.57
15–30	4.06
30–45	8.46
45–55	8.10
> 55	69.81

Daily meteorological inputs to the SWAT model included precipitation (pcp), temperature (tmp), solar radiation (slr), relative humidity (hmd), and wind speed (wnd), which are required to drive key hydrologic and energy balance processes. These data were obtained from the the Central Weather Administration and were used to simulate rainfall–runoff generation, evapotranspiration, and other water balance components at a daily time step.

Table 3. Locations, elevation, and meteorological variables used from monitoring stations.

Station ID	Location (TWD97 X, Y)	Data used	Elevation (m)
C0F861	274743.6756, 2682457.531	pcp, hmd, slr, tmp, wnd	2215
C0F0E0	295113.3736, 2695376.588	pcp, hmd, wnd	3557
C0T790	282112.7848, 2675671.593	pcp, hmd, wnd	2830
C0H9C0	277698.6156, 2670936.012	pcp, hmd, wnd	3402
C0F9Z0	277252.7397, 2698108.209	pcp, hmd, wnd	3193
C0F9Y0	280805.7699, 2702982.873	pcp, hmd	3313
C1F9W0	269319.181, 2683253.261	pcp	1970

Crop management was defined based on tea cultivation, as tea is the dominant crop in the study area. Thus, management inputs in SWAT were parameterized to represent tea plants. Fertilizer application rates were determined based on Taiwan’s Crop Fertilizer Handbook [5], specifically for mature tea plants of approximately five years of age.

Point source inputs in the watershed were incorporated to represent localized pollutant discharges affecting water quality. Three point sources were considered in this study, including the Lishan Drainage Channel, the Huashan Wastewater Treatment Plant, and the Lishan Wastewater Treatment Plant. The locations of these sources were specified based on available spatial data (Table 4), and their inputs were included in the SWAT model to account for external nutrient and pollutant loading.

2.2 SWAT model setup

Watershed delineation was performed automatically using the QSWAT3 interface within QGIS to define the drainage network and sub-basin boundaries of the Deji Reservoir catchment. The DEM was used as the primary input to derive flow direction and flow accumulation grids. Based on these grids, the stream network was generated.

Following stream network definition, the watershed outlet at the Deji Reservoir was specified, and additional points representing three point sources and two gauging stations were incorporated into the model (see Table 4). These points were used to define inlet and monitoring locations to ensure that the stream network and subsequent sub-basin delineation reflect observed data locations within the catchment.

Table 4. Locations of outlets, gauging stations, and point sources in the Deji Reservoir catchment.

ID	Type	Location (TWD97 X, Y)	Description
1	Gauging Station	281507.97, 2691463.42	Chichiawan station
2	Gauging Station	279272.15, 2688661.57	Hehuanshan station
3	Reservoir Inlet	275450.373, 2685512.049	Entry point to the reservoir
4	Watershed Outlet	267891.120, 2683903.609	Watershed outlet
-	Point Source	275201.812, 2683249.623	Lishan Drainage Channel
-	Point Source	279773.659, 2690109.785	Huanshan Wastewater Treatment Plant
-	Point Source	274290.394, 2683463.382	Lishan Wastewater Treatment Plant

The watershed was then subdivided into 31 sub-basins based on the defined drainage network and specified outlet and inlet points. Each sub-basin represents a spatial unit defined by topography, within which surface runoff is routed toward a common outlet, and serves as the basis for subsequent HRU definition.

HRUs were defined within each sub-basin to represent unique combinations of land use, soil type, and slope class. These spatial datasets were overlaid within the QSWAT3 interface to generate HRUs that capture the heterogeneity of the watershed. No threshold values were applied during HRU definition; therefore, all combinations of land use, soil, and slope were retained. This approach preserves the full spatial variability of watershed characteristics, although it increases model complexity and computational demand. As a result, a total of 703 HRUs were generated for the entire catchment.

The resulting HRUs serve as the fundamental computational units in the SWAT model, within which hydrological processes such as surface runoff, evapotranspiration, infiltration, and pollutant transport are simulated. This discretization allows the model to account for spatial variability in watershed properties and supports detailed representation of hydrological and water quality processes within the catchment.

3 Model calibration and validation

3.1 Calibration methodology

Model calibration and validation were conducted using observed data from two gauging stations, Chichiawan and Hehuanshan.

The SWAT Calibration and Uncertainty Program (SWAT-CUP) was employed to calibrate the model using streamflow and water quality data for the period 2014–2018 [6]. Calibration was performed using the SUFI-2 algorithm, which iteratively adjusts model parameters within predefined ranges to reduce discrepancies between simulated and observed values while accounting for parameter uncertainty through multiple simulations [7]. SUFI-2 was selected for its computational

efficiency and its ability to quantify parameter uncertainty.

Following calibration, the model was validated against an independent dataset for the period 2019–2021 to assess its predictive capability under different conditions.

3.2 Observed data processing

Observed hydrological and water quality data were processed prior to model calibration to ensure consistency with SWAT output variables and temporal resolution. Streamflow observations were obtained at a daily time step from the two gauging stations (Chichiawan and Hehuanshan) and used directly for calibration and validation.

In contrast, sediment and total phosphorus (TP) observations were available as discrete concentration measurements and therefore required conversion to continuous load estimates. To achieve this, rating curves were developed to relate measured concentrations to corresponding stream discharge. Paired observations of discharge and constituent concentration were used to derive empirical relationships of the form:

$$L = aQ^b \quad (1)$$

where L is the constituent load (sediment or TP), Q is discharge, and a and b are regression coefficients.

The resulting rating curves were applied to the discharge time series to estimate continuous sediment and TP loads. Daily sediment loads were computed to match the temporal resolution of the model output. For TP, daily loads were first estimated using the rating curves and subsequently aggregated to monthly values to reduce short-term variability and improve comparability with observed data. The derived rating curves for sediment and TP at both stations are shown in Figures 2 and 3, respectively. The rating curves indicate a strong relationship between discharge and sediment load, particularly at Hehuanshan, while greater scatter is observed for TP, reflecting higher variability in nutrient transport processes.

Figure 2. Sediment rating curves relating discharge to sediment load for (a) Hehuanshan and (b) Chichiawan stations. Observed data are shown as points, and dashed lines represent fitted power-law relationships.

Figure 3. TP rating curves relating discharge to TP load for (a) Hehuanshan and (b) Chichiawan stations. Points represent observed data and dashed lines indicate fitted power-law relationships.

Uncertainty in the rating curve approach arises from limited sampling frequency, particularly during high-flow events when sediment and nutrient transport can be highly variable. In addition, the assumption of a single discharge–concentration relationship may not fully capture seasonal or event-based variability. Despite these limitations, the rating curves provide a practical and widely used method for estimating continuous water quality loads required for model calibration.

3.3 Performance evaluation metrics

Model performance was evaluated using the Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE), coefficient of determination (R^2), and percent bias (PBIAS), based on the best-performing parameter set identified during calibration [8]. These metrics are widely used to assess the accuracy and reliability of hydrological models.

The NSE is defined as:

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^{obs} - Q_i^{sim})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^{obs} - \overline{Q^{obs}})^2} \quad (2)$$

where Q_i^{obs} and Q_i^{sim} are the observed and simulated values, respectively, and $\overline{Q^{obs}}$ is the mean of observed values. NSE ranges from $-\infty$ to 1, with values closer to 1 indicating better model performance.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) describes the strength of the linear relationship between observed and simulated values, with values closer to 1 indicating stronger agreement.

Percent bias (PBIAS) is defined as:

$$PBIAS = 100 \times \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^{sim} - Q_i^{obs})}{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i^{obs}} \quad (3)$$

PBIAS measures the average tendency of the simulated values to overestimate or underestimate observations. Positive values indicate underestimation, while negative values indicate overestimation.

Model performance was interpreted based on commonly used criteria, where NSE values greater than 0.5 are generally considered satisfactory for hydrological modeling [8].

3.4 Calibrated parameters

The final calibrated parameter values obtained from the SUFI-2 calibration procedure are presented in Table 5. These parameters represent key hydrological, sediment, and nutrient processes within the watershed and were adjusted to improve agreement between simulated and observed data during the calibration period.

Table 5. Final calibrated parameter values.

Parameter	Description	Type	Value
CN2.mgt	Curve number for runoff	relative	-0.396889
ESCO.hru	Soil evaporation factor	replace	0.79220
GW_REVAP.gw	Groundwater revap coefficient	replace	0.06976
OV_N.hru	Overland flow roughness	relative	0.17345
SLSUBBSN.hru	Subbasin slope length	relative	-0.311396
SOL_K().sol	Soil hydraulic conductivity	replace	14.18743
ALPHA_BF.gw	Baseflow recession constant	replace	0.39566
CH_N2.rte	Channel roughness	replace	0.34370
CH_K2.rte	Channel hydraulic conductivity	replace	10.96878
HRU_SLP.hru	HRU slope steepness	relative	-0.309807
USLE_K().sol	Soil erodibility factor	replace	0.00258
USLE_P.mgt _____	AGRL Support practice (agriculture)	replace	0.85723
USLE_P.mgt _____	WETN Support practice (wetland)	replace	0.26940
USLE_P.mgt _____	WETF Support practice (forest wetland)	replace	0.30390
USLE_P.mgt _____	WATR Support practice (water)	replace	0.501679
USLE_P.mgt _____	UTRN Support practice (transport)	replace	0.78039
USLE_P.mgt _____	URMD Support practice (urban medium)	replace	0.65438
USLE_P.mgt _____	URLD Support practice (urban low)	replace	0.357599
USLE_P.mgt _____	FRSD Support practice (deciduous forest)	replace	0.29111
USLE_P.mgt _____	FRST Support practice (mixed forest)	replace	0.03693
USLE_P.mgt _____	FRSE Support practice (evergreen forest)	replace	0.26002
CH_COV1.rte ^a	Channel cover factor	replace	0.24797
CH_COV1.rte ^b	Channel cover factor	replace	0.011659
CH_COV2.rte ^a	Channel erodibility factor	replace	0.11858
CH_COV2.rte ^b	Channel erodibility factor	replace	0.85847
GWSOLP.gw ^a	Groundwater soluble P	replace	0.03253
GWSOLP.gw ^b	Groundwater soluble P	replace	0.01867
SOL_ORGP().chm ^a	Soil organic P	replace	0.32882
SOL_ORGP().chm ^b	Soil organic P	replace	0.31233
PHOSKD.bsn	P partitioning coefficient	replace	198.85937

^a Subbasin group 1: 10, 14–15, 17–20, 22, 24–25, 27

^b Subbasin group 2: 1–9, 11–13, 16, 21, 23, 26, 28–31

The calibrated parameters represent key hydrological, sediment, and nutrient processes within the watershed.

Hydrological processes were primarily controlled by parameters such as CN2, ESCO, AL-

PHA_BF, GW_REVAP, and SOL_K. The curve number (CN2) governs surface runoff generation, while ESCO (soil evaporation compensation factor) controls the depth distribution of soil evaporation within the soil profile. ALPHA_BF defines the baseflow recession constant, influencing groundwater contribution to streamflow, and GW_REVAP controls the movement of water from the shallow aquifer to the root zone through capillary rise. Soil saturated hydraulic conductivity (SOL_K) affects infiltration and percolation processes. Additionally, HRU_SLP and SLSUBBSN describe slope steepness and slope length, respectively, affecting runoff generation and erosion processes.

Surface runoff and flow routing were further influenced by OV_N and channel parameters including CH_N2 and CH_K2. OV_N represents Manning’s roughness coefficient for overland flow, affecting flow resistance, while CH_N2 and CH_K2 control channel flow resistance and water loss from the channel to the underlying aquifer, respectively.

Sediment transport was adjusted using parameters such as USLE_K and USLE_P. The USLE_K factor represents soil erodibility, while USLE_P reflects conservation practices and varies by land use type. These parameters collectively influence soil erosion and sediment yield from different HRUs.

Channel erosion and sediment processes were further adjusted using CH_COV1 and CH_COV2, which represent channel cover and erodibility factors affecting sediment routing and channel erosion processes.

Nutrient processes, particularly phosphorus dynamics, were controlled by parameters such as PHOSKD, GWSOLP, and SOL_ORGP. PHOSKD is the phosphorus soil partitioning coefficient governing the distribution between dissolved and adsorbed phosphorus. GWSOLP represents soluble phosphorus concentrations in groundwater, while SOL_ORGP defines the organic phosphorus content within soil layers.

Among these, parameters related to runoff generation (CN2), baseflow processes (ALPHA_BF), and soil hydraulic properties (SOL_K) had the most significant influence on model performance. Overall, the selected parameters capture the dominant hydrological, sediment, and nutrient processes in the watershed and were adjusted during calibration to improve agreement between simulated and observed data.

4 Model results

Using the processed observational datasets described in Section 3.2, the performance of the calibrated SWAT model was evaluated for streamflow, sediment load, and total phosphorus at two gauging stations during both calibration (2014–2018) and validation (2019–2021) periods, as shown in Table 6. Streamflow and sediment load were assessed at a daily time step, while TP was evaluated using monthly aggregated values to reduce short-term variability and improve comparability with observed water quality data. Model performance was quantified using the NSE, R^2 , and PBIAS, which are commonly used metrics for hydrological model evaluation.

4.1 Streamflow

For streamflow simulation, the model achieved generally good performance at both stations. During calibration, NSE values ranged from 0.68 to 0.71, with corresponding R^2 values above 0.70, indicating a satisfactory representation of flow dynamics. Validation results remained stable, particularly at Chichiawan, where NSE (0.70) and R^2 (0.79) suggest consistent predictive capability. However, positive PBIAS values at both stations indicate a tendency to underestimate observed

Table 6. Watershed model performance using the best parameter set.

Station	Period	R^2	NSE	PBIAS (%)	Mean (sim.) [obs.] ^{1,2}
Streamflow					(m ³ /s)
Hehuanshan	Calibration	0.73	0.68	+15.7	6.62 [7.85]
	Validation	0.62	0.60	+22.7	5.07 [6.55]
Chichiawan	Calibration	0.71	0.71	+13.4	5.67 [6.54]
	Validation	0.79	0.70	+9.2	4.08 [4.49]
Daily sediment load					(tons)
Hehuanshan	Calibration	0.59	0.59	-0.1	0.86 [0.86]
	Validation	0.66	0.65	-6.9	0.66 [0.61]
Chichiawan	Calibration	0.46	0.42	+15.4	0.50 [0.59]
	Validation	0.71	0.70	+7.0	0.41 [0.44]
Monthly TP load					(kg)
Hehuanshan	Calibration	0.58	0.57	+0.31	296 [295]
	Validation	0.55	0.48	-17.13	214 [259]
Chichiawan	Calibration	0.46	0.33	-12.11	211 [240]
	Validation	0.86	0.67	-18.10	148 [180]

¹ Simulated values, ² Observed values.

streamflow, especially at Hehuanshan during validation (+22.7%). This may be attributed to challenges in capturing high-flow events or spatial variability in precipitation inputs in mountainous terrain. Discrepancies are particularly evident during peak flow events, reflecting the difficulty of representing extreme hydrological responses in steep mountainous catchments. The NSE values indicate good model performance according to established evaluation criteria [8], where NSE values greater than 0.5 are generally considered satisfactory for hydrological modeling, suggesting that the model is able to reliably reproduce the dominant hydrological processes in the watershed. Despite this, model performance remains within acceptable ranges for hydrological applications in mountainous catchments.

Figure 4. Comparison of observed and simulated streamflow for two monitoring stations during calibration and validation periods. Panels show (a) Hehuanshan Station calibration, (b) Hehuanshan Station validation, (c) Chichiawan Station calibration, and (d) Chichiawan Station validation. Observed streamflow is shown in blue, while simulated streamflow is shown in red.

4.2 Sediment load

Sediment load simulations were calibrated and validated for the same two stations. The model performed satisfactorily in both calibration and validation periods, as shown in Figure 5.

For sediment load, model performance was moderate but improved during validation. At Hehuanshan, NSE increased from 0.59 (calibration) to 0.65 (validation), with minimal bias, indicating reliable simulation of sediment transport processes. At Chichiawan, performance during calibration was lower (NSE = 0.42), but improved substantially during validation (NSE = 0.70), suggesting that the calibrated parameter set better captured sediment dynamics under different hydrological conditions. The remaining bias and variability may reflect uncertainties in erosion processes, slope representation, and sediment routing. Overall, these results indicate satisfactory model performance for sediment simulation.

Figure 5. Comparison of observed and simulated sediment yield for two monitoring stations during calibration and validation periods. Panels show (a) Hehuanshan Station calibration, (b) Hehuanshan Station validation, (c) Chichiawan Station calibration, and (d) Chichiawan Station validation. Observed sediment is shown in blue, while simulated sediment is shown in red.

The model was able to capture the timing and magnitude of major sediment peaks, although some discrepancies remain during high-flow events, reflecting the nonlinear nature of erosion and sediment transport processes.

4.3 Total phosphorus load

For TP, model performance was comparatively weaker and more variable. TP loads were evaluated at a monthly time step following aggregation of daily estimates derived from rating curves. At Hehuanshan, NSE values were moderate (0.57 during calibration and 0.48 during validation), with a shift from near-zero bias to underestimation during validation. At Chichiawan, calibration performance was limited (NSE = 0.33), but validation results improved significantly (NSE = 0.67 and $R^2 = 0.86$), indicating improved model performance under the hydrological conditions observed during the validation period. The larger discrepancies in TP simulations likely arise from the complexity of nutrient processes, including interactions among soil, sediment, and point source inputs, as well as potential uncertainties in input data such as fertilizer application and wastewater discharge.

Figure 6. Comparison of observed and simulated total phosphorus for two monitoring stations during calibration and validation periods. Panels show (a) Hehuanshan Station calibration (2014–2018), (b) Hehuanshan Station validation (2019–2021), (c) Chichiawan Station calibration (2014–2018), and (d) Chichiawan Station validation (2019–2021). Observed total phosphorus is shown in blue, while simulated total phosphorus is shown in red. Values are expressed as monthly totals in kilograms per month.

5 Model limitations and uncertainties

While the SWAT model provides a reasonable representation of hydrological and water quality processes in the Deji Reservoir catchment, several limitations and sources of uncertainty should be acknowledged.

First, input data limitations contribute to model uncertainty. The soil dataset represents the watershed as a single soil type, which may not fully capture spatial variability in soil properties affecting infiltration, runoff, and nutrient transport.

Second, model structural assumptions introduce uncertainty. The discretization of the watershed into subbasins and HRUs simplifies spatial heterogeneity, and the use of lumped parameters within HRUs may not fully represent localized processes. However, a zero-threshold approach was applied during HRU definition to preserve spatial detail.

Third, uncertainties are associated with parameter calibration. While the SUFI-2 algorithm accounts for parameter uncertainty through iterative simulations, the calibrated parameter set represents an optimal solution within predefined ranges rather than a unique or physically exact representation of watershed processes.

Finally, water quality simulations, particularly for TP, are subject to higher uncertainty due

to the complexity of nutrient processes. These include interactions among soil, sediment, and hydrological pathways, as well as uncertainties in input data such as fertilizer application rates and point source discharge characteristics.

Despite these limitations, the model demonstrates sufficient performance for simulating watershed-scale hydrological and sediment processes. However, caution is needed when interpreting nutrient-related results, and further improvements in input data and process representation would enhance model reliability.

6 Conclusion

This study developed and applied a SWAT model to simulate hydrological and water quality processes in the Deji Reservoir catchment. The model was successfully calibrated and validated using observed streamflow, sediment load, and TP data from two gauging stations.

Model performance was satisfactory for streamflow and sediment load, with Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency values generally above 0.5 and demonstrating good agreement between simulated and observed data. These results suggest that the model captures the dominant hydrological processes and sediment transport dynamics within the watershed. In contrast, TP simulations exhibited greater variability and lower performance, reflecting the increased complexity and uncertainty associated with nutrient processes and input data.

Despite these limitations, the model demonstrates sufficient reliability for representing watershed-scale processes and provides a useful tool for analyzing watershed behavior. The inclusion of detailed spatial discretization and point source inputs further enhances its ability to simulate the heterogeneity of the catchment.

The developed SWAT model provides a suitable framework for future applications, including scenario analysis of land use change, climate variability, and watershed management strategies. The results support its use as a decision-support tool for improving water resource management and mitigating sediment and nutrient impacts in the Deji Reservoir catchment.

Future work could focus on improving nutrient input data and incorporating higher-resolution soil and land management information to enhance model accuracy.

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